

Vox Day and Baron Münchhausen: Trilemmas and Right-Wing Epistemology

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Abstract

While pseudoscience and science denial have long been associated with fringe political movements, in recent years both have become more strongly associated with right-wing ideologies. Within the same time period, political views once regarded as fringe have become increasingly influential particularly within the politics of the USA. This paper discusses an attempt by a notable figure associated with the “alt-right” and “Christian Nationalism” to develop a general epistemological approach aligned with the broader ideology.

This paper examines one attempt to apply the approach to a historical question in epistemology (the Munchhausen or Agrippan Trilemma) and discusses the ways in which this approach fails in multiple ways.

Background

Approach

In this paper we will be examining the claims of Vox Day in relation to his epistemology and to the philosophical problem of justification. In this background section we will give a brief overview of Vox Day, his recent epistemological writing and the problem of justification known as the Münchhausen Trilemma.

Note that the overview of Vox Day will outline some of his views that many readers will find morally reprehensible or even implicitly discrediting. We are outlining his views not as a lazy way of discrediting him, it is possible for a person with reprehensible views to have genuine insights about truth (although we don't believe that Day has made a genuine insight). We will discuss his epistemology on its own merits. However, we believe the context of Day's epistemological project is relevant for people to understand why Day might be attempting to establish his theory of justification.

When reading the papers produced by Vox Day there are times when his meaning is unclear to us. In those circumstances we have attempted to be generous in interpreting his meaning so as to assume meanings that are consistent with his other statements and which put his argument on a stronger footing. We note that the papers we are examining are presented as working papers and hence may not represent Day's final version of his arguments.

Vox Day

Vox Day aka Theodore Beale is a publisher, game designer, musician, author, columnist and right-wing blogger. He has described his political beliefs as “Christian Nationalism” and has espoused race-based nationalism and hostility towards immigration. He has openly praised the

neo-Nazi mass murderer Anders Breivik who killed 77 people (including 30 teenagers) in 2011. Day regards these murders as a legitimate act of war.

Day takes a contrarian stance towards many commonly held beliefs across multiple disciplines, including the history of the Holocaust, the moon landings, the authorship of Shakespeare's plays, the efficacy of vaccination, modern economics, and evolution by natural selection. However, it would be incorrect to characterise his position as philosophical scepticism. Day attests that he follows the modes of reasoning taught by Aristotle and that Western Civilisation has become unmoored from reason by the influence of Enlightenment thinkers such as Immanuel Kant. Day regards Kant in particular as a malign influence on modern thought.

In the past Day has been associated with so-called "culture war" movements such as GamerGate, the Sad/Rabid Puppies, Pizzagate and Qanon. More recently, Day has attempted to present his views in a more systematic way and has been producing books and papers with the aid of a Large Language Model (Claude) that resemble academic writing. These efforts were initially directed at an attempt to disprove the theory of evolution by natural selection. More recently, Day has attempted to present his own theory of epistemology.

Veriphysics and the Triveritas

Vox Day's most recent collaboration with the LLM Claude is a series of essays on his own theory of how truth should be established. The overall project is called "veriphysics" but the specific approach to establishing truth is called the 'triveritas'. A full account of the triveritas method will be given later but a rough sketch of Day's idea is that scientific theories or even just basic claims about the world should be judged against logic, mathematics and empirical observation. In this rough sketch form, the idea sounds neither novel nor controversial. However, Day believes he has a specific method of applying all three sources of truth.

The triveritas makes no direct reference to God or divinity. However, Day's veriphysics is explicitly grounded in Day's conception of Christianity as outlined in a recent essay VERIPHYSICS: THE TREATISE 022 (V. A Sound Grounding in Christian Metaphysics):

"Christian metaphysics grounds truth in the Logos, in the divine reason that creates and sustains all things. The world is intelligible because it is the product of intelligence. Truth is not an abstraction floating free of reality; it is an attribute of God Himself, participated in by creatures insofar as they know. The correspondence between mind and world that makes knowledge possible is not a happy accident; it is a consequence of both mind and world being created by the same rational God. We can know because we are made in the image of one who knows perfectly."

Readers may wonder why, if a divine Logos is held to be the ultimate source of knowledge (a common belief historically among many figures in Western philosophy) that there is any need to look for other forms of justification. It is reasonable to assume that Day would like to be able to demonstrate religious truths using the triveritas without assuming the existence of God or gods. Hence, while "divine reason" underpins Day's metaphysics, his triveritas remains god-free.

The Agrippan Modes and the Münchhausen Trilemma

Sextus Empiricus was a 2nd century Greek philosopher associated with Pyrrhonism – a form of scepticism that holds that we should suspend judgement on the truth of any claim. Sextus Empiricus attributed to another Pyrrhonist, Agrippa, five modes that all arguments eventually retreat to. Three of those modes have since become known as the Münchhausen Trilemma – named after the fictional Baron Münchhausen who escaped from a swamp by pulling himself up by his own hair.

German philosopher Hans Albert re-presented the trilemma in his 1968 book *Treatise on Critical Reason*. Albert expanded on Karl Popper's concept of falsification as alternate approach to the epistemology of science that avoids some of the issues of justification. Those issues could be summed up using Albert's version of the trilemma.

This leads to a situation with three alternatives, all of which appear unacceptable: in other words, to a trilemma which, in view of the analogy existing between our problem and one which that celebrated and mendacious baron once had to solve, I should like to call the Münchhausen trilemma. For, obviously, one must choose here between

- 1. an infinite regress, which seems to arise from the necessity to go further and further back in the search for foundations, and which, since it is in practice impossible, affords no secure basis;*
- 2. a logical circle in the deduction, which arises because, in the process of justification, statements are used which were characterized before as in need of foundation, so that they can provide no secure basis; and, finally,*
- 3. the breaking-off of the process at a particular point, which, admittedly, can always be done in principle, but involves an arbitrary suspension of the principle of sufficient justification.*

An infinite regress obviously provides no foundation for reason. Circular reasoning is clearly flawed. Inevitably, argues Albert, people will assert some point as a self evident truth from which everything else can be deduced. However, whatever point is picked, it can still be doubted.

Vox Day argues, in a recent working paper, that his method of the triveritas defeats the trilemma and additionally that the trilemma has always been flawed. It is this argument that we shall be examining.

The Triveritas

Between 21 February and 22 February, Vox Day posted four papers on the Zenodo repository.

- A Mathematical Proof of the Triveritas: The Necessity and Superiority of the Three-Condition Criterion
- A Logical Proof of the Triveritas: A Deductive Demonstration from First Principles
- An Empirical Proof of the Triveritas: A Systematic Test Against the Historical Record
- Solving the Agrippan Trilemma: Triveritas and the Third Horn

Our main focus is the final paper "Solving the Agrippan Trilemma" but the three preceding papers provide important information on Day's methods. We will follow the text of that paper with occasional excursions into the others to seek clarification of what Day means.

Day's paper opens by presenting the background to Münchhausen Trilemma. While he makes reference to Hans Albert, Day prefers the name Agrippan Trilemma, although his formulation of the trilemma appears to be closer to Albert's. Day then presents a conventional summary of other approaches to justification:

"Foundationalism accepts dogmatic stopping, identifying certain beliefs as properly basic and terminating the chain there. Coherentism accepts circularity, holding that beliefs are justified by mutual support within a web. Infinitism accepts the regress, arguing that an infinite chain of reasons is not inherently defective. Each of these frameworks treats one horn as a feature rather than a defect. None defeats the Trilemma."

Day does not mention positivism but arguably the same criticism holds for positivism as he outlines for foundationalism: that a stopping point is justified. More oddly, given that he cites Hans Albert's 1968 *Treatise on Critical Reason*, Day does not mention Albert's use of falsifiability as a way of avoiding the trilemma altogether. A discussion of Albert's views are beyond the scope of our paper but we note that it is odd that Day makes no mention of it.

Day then contends that his paper has solved the trilemma and that his solution rests on one of the premises of the trilemma being false. Day contends that there is an amphiboly (an ambiguity) in the trilemma specifically in the third point.

"The amphiboly is this: the Trilemma treats "terminates" as equivalent to "terminates arbitrarily." It assumes that any stopping point is an unjustified stopping point, that all termination is epistemically equal, that there is no distinction between stopping because you have run out of reasons and stopping because you have run out of unchecked dimensions. This conflation is not argued for in the Trilemma. It is assumed. And it is false."

This an odd claim to make as Hans Albert's formulation (at least in the English translation) contains no ambiguity but explicitly uses the term "arbitrary" (see the earlier quotation). It is possible that other phrasings of the trilemma may be worded ambiguously but Day cites Albert. Later in the paper he discusses Albert's wording but only in German fragments.

Day's resolution of the third horn of the trilemma is that his stopping point isn't arbitrary. This resolution to the trilemma is not new or original as foundationalism makes a similar claim e.g. that there are some self-evident truths that need no further justification.

The objection to this claim is well known also, that self-evident truths may not be self-evident. Attempts at axiomatisation in mathematics in particular has resulted in deep questions on whether specific axioms required to make a given axiomatic system be fruitful are actually self-evident. In the oldest axiomatic system in mathematics, Euclid's axioms of geometry, the question of the parallel postulate (needed among other things to show that the angles of a triangle add up to 180 degrees) was of active interest since 300 BCE. It wasn't until the 19th century that mathematicians began experimenting with alternative versions of this axiom to investigate alternative geometries. This in turn led to an increased interest in foundational questions in mathematics.

Day then goes onto describe his triveritas methods and says something curious:

"The Triveritas demonstrates that it is false. The Triveritas holds that warranted assent requires the simultaneous satisfaction of three independently necessary conditions: logical validity (L), mathematical coherence (M), and empirical anchoring (E). Each dimension terminates at its own bedrock: L at logical axioms, M at mathematical axioms, E at observation. The Triveritas takes the third horn. It terminates. But it terminates at three independent stopping points of fundamentally different kinds, each constraining the others. The probability of all three stopping points being wrong in a way that produces a coherent false positive is strictly lower than the probability of any single stopping point being wrong."

We have not found a place where Day explains what he means by "warranted assent" but given that his description of the trevitas is in terms of probability, it would appear to me a provisional acceptance that some claim is true that may later be falsified or further affirmed. It is very reasonable to take such a stance and Day has expanded further on his own form of realism on his blog in an essay *Veriphysics: The Treatise 020 (III. Aletheian Realism: The Metaphysical Foundation)*:

“It does not claim that human knowledge is infallible, complete, or perspectiveless. It acknowledges that we know from particular positions, through particular faculties, with particular limitations. The glass through which we see is real—it shapes and constrains what we perceive. But what we perceive through it is also real. The task of inquiry is to clarify the glass, to correct for its distortions, to bring the image into sharper focus—not to imagine that we can dispense with the glass altogether and see as God sees.”

What is odd is that this by itself undermines any concern about Münchhausen Trilemma or indeed whether a stopping point is self-evident, justified or arbitrary. A provisional acceptance that some claim is probably true is sufficiently squishy that an infinite regress peters out, potential circles of reasons never quite join up and stopping points might occur due to a lack of interest. The extreme scepticism offered by the Phyrhonists is a challenge to the certainty of truth.

We are not sure how to describe an argument which incorrectly claims to have resolved a challenge when that challenge did not apply in the first place. Nevertheless, Day continues with an extended section on how the triveritas is distinct from Foundationalism.

“Consider a foundationalist who terminates at a single self-evident belief. The Trilemma's critique is devastating against this foundationalist because the stopping point is genuinely unchecked. If the self-evident belief is wrong, nothing in the system detects the error.”

The right-wing “Objectivist” writer Ayn Rand was fond of saying $A=A$ as the basis of all logic. Arguably, she might be considered as a Foundationalist who justified her beliefs with a single self-evident belief. Practically, of course, Rand would not be able to derive any additional claims from a simple tautology, nor could any Foundationalist rest all justification on one self-evident belief. Descartes may have offered that his own thinking was evidence of his own existence but he also assumed that logical reasoning held.

Day claims his triveritas has three stopping points and hence is secure. We believe this may be an example of the Spinal Tap Amplifier Fallacy, where a larger number is assumed to be better.

“Now consider the Triveritas. It terminates at three stopping points: logical axioms, mathematical axioms, and observation. Each stopping point belongs to a different chain (deductive, quantitative, observational). Each chain is independent: the logical proof uses no mathematics beyond set containment and no empirical data; the mathematical proof works within probability theory without relying on deductive syllogism as a method; the empirical proof tests predictions against historical observation without invoking either the logical or mathematical proof's apparatus. A false claim that sneaks past one stopping point must also sneak past the other two, which operate by different methods on different aspects of the claim.”

This argument mixes not just Foundationalism (an appeal to axioms) but also Coherentism (later in the paper, Day will argue that his triveritas is not Coherentism but we will get to that in turn). also raises many questions about what Day might mean by “logical axioms” and “mathematical axioms”. From the perspective of foundations and justification, all he has done is multiply his problems BUT also, it doesn't matter because the outcome is only a provisional belief. Readers may also have additional questions such as how is mathematics independent of logic and if the logical analysis contains no empirical data then what is it analysing? We ask for the reader's patience on these questions.

The Amphiboly in the Third Horn

The section after the Introduction continues to discuss Day’s claim that the third horn is ambiguous. Day does not discuss the English translation of Albert’s version of the trilemma but does discuss two phrases from the original German. Day does not quote the whole German phrase. Neither, of the authors of the essay you are reading speak German but we have read the published English translation and it quite clearly uses the word “arbitrary”:

the breaking-off of the process at a particular point, which, admittedly, can always be done in principle, but involves an arbitrary suspension of the principle of sufficient justification.

Day is, of course, free to argue that his breaking off point is not arbitrary but his own defence of the triveritas states that it only identifies what might be probably true. By definition, the triveritas, if it does anything, breaks off before establishing full justification which is what the trilemma predicts.

This section adds very little and is oddly repetitive, which is a feature of LLM generated text, so possibly this was primarily generated by Claude.

The Triveritas Architecture

The third section provides more detail on the triveritas. We will give longer quotes here with some discussion.

Day describes the triveritas as three conditions that any claim must satisfy to merit “warranted assent”.

Logical Validity (L). *The claim's conclusion follows deductively from its premises, and its inferential structure possesses explanatory coherence: the premises bear a principled, non-ad-hoc relationship to the conclusion. A collection of independently fitted curves, each matching a separate observation but sharing no common explanatory structure, does not satisfy L even if each curve is internally valid.*

Mathematical Coherence (M). *The claim's quantitative structure is internally consistent. Its operations are well-defined, its parameters are finite and computable in principle, and its mathematical predictions do not contradict its own axioms. A claim that requires division by zero, produces divergent series where convergence is needed, or demands quantities that exceed physical constraints imposed by its own model fails M.*

Empirical Anchoring (E). *The claim makes at least one prediction that has been tested against observation and not refuted. Anchoring requires contact with independently verifiable data, not merely consistency with data already used to construct the claim*

Of these three, we think Mathematical Coherence and Empirical Anchoring are relatively clear in meaning. The term “claim” itself is unclear but that may just be a poor choice of words. In the examples given in the related paper *An Empirical Proof of the Triveritas: A Systematic Test Against the Historical Record* the “claims” are complex scientific models/theories. For example, the historical “Caloric Theory of Heat” is used as an example that fails the triveritas. So “claim” should be taken to mean a scientific hypothesis with multiple elements to it not just a single sentence proposition.

“Logical Validity” appears to mean multiple things.

- The claim's conclusion follows deductively from its premises,

- its inferential structure possesses explanatory coherence
- the premises bear a principled, non-ad-hoc relationship to the conclusion

The first of those three is what would normally be meant by logical validity. The second two points (one may be a clarification of the other) appear to be talking about some semantic aspect of the claim. This interpretation of “logical validity” is used in one of the examples in *An Empirical Proof of the Triveritas*. In that paper, Day argues that the Ptolemaic Epicycles model of planetary orbits fails the Logical Validity criteria of the triveritas:

“L failed: The system had no logical unity. Each new observational anomaly required an additional epicycle with independently fitted parameters. There was no principled stopping condition, no causal mechanism, and no unifying structure connecting the various adjustments. The geocentric premise was assumed, never tested, and the epicycles were ad hoc accommodations.”

These are legitimate criticism of epicycles but they aren’t based on logical deduction. Explanatory power or thematic consistency or parsimonious explanation are things we might want out of a scientific theory but they are notoriously difficult to establish as formal rules. They can’t be deduced logically.

In Day’s companion paper *A Mathematical Proof of the Triveritas: The Necessity and Superiority of the Three-Condition Criterion*, he uses the example of curve fitting as an example:

“High-degree polynomial curve-fitting provides the structurally pure case. A polynomial of degree $n-1$ passes exactly through n data points (M satisfied) and is empirically confirmed on the training set (E satisfied). But the model has no logical unity: each coefficient is an independent accommodation of a data point, not a consequence of any explanatory framework. Predictions outside the training set are typically catastrophic. Overfitting is the canonical failure mode of $M \cap E$ without L .”

Finding a mathematical formula that fits data points is an interesting question about determining truth and we agree with Day that simply fitting a polynomial with sufficient coefficients (or say a Bezier curve) provides less insights that developing an underlying model with some explanatory power i.e. where the mathematics reflects the underlying process that resulted in the pattern of the data. Finding such models requires many things and logical reasoning is one of them but it can’t typically be done simply by applying syllogisms. Extending the term “logic” to the kind of creative investigation needed to develop a meaningful mathematical model is itself a process of inquiry that requires further application of mathematics, empirical observation as well as knowledge about potentially related processes.

We have debated whether Day regards the [Principle of Sufficient Reason](#) as one of the axioms of logic. There have been times when it was regarded as one of the rules of thought. However, this principle is associated with Spinoza and Gottfried Leibniz, who are both regarded as early enlightenment figures and Day’s project is overtly anti-Enlightenment. Day doesn’t mention the Principle of Sufficient Reason in these papers or on his essays about Veriphysics. The principle might get Day someday to what he is intending here though. Leibniz’s version is suggestive:

“by virtue of which we consider that we can find no true or existent fact [fait], no true assertion [énonciation véritable], without there being a sufficient reason why it is thus and not otherwise, although most of the time these reasons cannot be known to us.”

We aren't sure that even with this principle, that Day's use of "logical validity" makes sense but we are open to hearing arguments why it might. Elsewhere in the paper, Day is clear that when he says logical validity he is talking about deductive reason via syllogisms.

Triveritas details from other papers

Day provides greater details of his underlying theory in some of the associated papers. We will draw from *A Logical Proof of the Triveritas: A Deductive Demonstration from First Principles* to detail Day's argument.

This paper breaks down his argument into more abstract principles:

D1. Claim. A claim is any well-formed declarative proposition capable of being true or false.

D2. Epistemic filter. An epistemic filter is a criterion that partitions the set of all claims into two non-empty classes: those that satisfy it and those that do not.

D3. Truth-tracking. A filter F is truth-tracking if, among the claims it excludes, at least some are false, and among the claims it retains, at least some are true. That is: F does not exclude all truth, and F does not retain all falsehood.

D4. Independence. Two filters F and G are independent if each excludes at least one false claim that the other does not exclude. That is: there exists a false claim that fails F but satisfies G , and there exists a false claim that fails G but satisfies F .

D5. Mutual independence. Three filters are mutually independent if every pair among them is independent, and additionally, for each filter F_k , there exists a false claim that satisfies the other two filters but fails F_k . That is: no two filters jointly entail the third.

D6. Epistemic superiority. A criterion A is epistemically superior to a criterion B if and only if: (i) every false claim admitted by A is also admitted by B , (ii) there exists at least one false claim admitted by B that is not admitted by A , and (iii) A admits at least one true claim.

Notably, in this paper "claim" is defined as a proposition. This is at odds with how "claim" is used in the trilemma paper and in the empirical examples paper. It is also less clear how logic applies at the level of a single proposition. Is Day suggesting he is using predicate logic?

D2 defines an epistemic filter as anything that separates claims into two sets. This is very broad but not unreasonable. Let's call the two categories as YES and NO depending on whether they satisfy the filter.

D3 defines truth tracking in a way that feels counter-intuitive. In the YES category there should be some true claims. In the NO category there should be some false claims. By this definition, a filter that randomly assigns claims to either category would count as Truth Tracking. Is this what Day intended?

In the companion paper *A Mathematical Proof of the Triveritas: The Necessity and Superiority of the Three-Condition Criterion* Day defines "truth tracking" differently.

"Axiom 4 (Truth-tracking). Each filter is positively correlated with truth. That is, for each $F \in \{L, M, E\}$:

$$P(T | F) > P(T)$$

This says that each filter does better than chance at selecting true claims over false ones. The axiom is not merely plausible but definitive of what it means for something to qualify as an epistemic filter at all. A filter that did not preferentially retain true claims would not be an epistemic criterion; it would be noise. The burden falls on

anyone who would deny this axiom to explain what epistemic work L, M, or E could possibly be doing if it is not truth-tracking”

In this definition, a filter is only truth tracking if it selects true claims more often than false claims. Day even disparages the idea that an epistemic filter could mean anything but this, which is ironic because in his other paper an epistemic filter would be truth tracking if it selected one true claim in a thousand while selecting most false claims.

Day does anticipate objections on this point and later in the paper:

“The logical proof is weaker than the mathematical proof in one specific respect. It establishes that the triple conjunction admits strictly fewer false claims than any proper subset. It does not establish that the triple conjunction has a higher truth-to-falsehood ratio than any proper subset. These are not the same claim.”

Despite this, Day uses the same term “truth tracking” and in one paper uses it for a filter that could potentially work on arbitrary criteria (“is this claim about fish?”). If we accept the D3 definition, Day’s paper would need additional criteria to avoid silly or random filters. So we will assume that “Axiom 4” is what he means by “truth tracking”. The issue appears to be that he didn’t want to use any mathematical concepts in his “logic” proof. This is excessive caution on Day’s part, logic, maths and even empirical observation are not wholly separate domains and it is silly to pretend that they are. It would not increase the flaws in Day’s reasoning if he uses a little maths, as a treat, in his logic proof. The alternative is to either fix D3 or to add more axioms to fix D3.

D4, D5 and D6 all make sense.

Day then offers a proof of the effectiveness of the triveritas. The proof uses a simple property of sets. Basically, L (logic), M (maths) and E (empirical observation) each separately sort claims into two categories: Satisfies the filter and Does Not Satisfy the filter. Day argues that intersection of the three satisfies filters is epistemically superior to any one or any pair of the filters.

Day’s proof does not appeal to any property of the filters that he hasn’t defined nor assert any assumption about the space of claims. This means we can test the proof by imagining three filters with the defined properties, operating over a small space of claims. The choices are arbitrary but if they satisfy the given rules, they will test the logic and outcome of Day’s proof.

Let C be a set of claims, some of which are intrinsically true and some of which are intrinsically false. $C = \{t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8, t9, f1, f2, f3, f4, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9\}$ where all claims with a t are true and all claims with an f are false.

Let L^* , M^* and E^* be three epistemic filters as defined by D1 (above). The following table shows how the three filters group the set of claims.

Filter	Satisfied	Not Satisfied
L^*	t1, t2, t3, f1, f2, f3	t4, t5, t6, t7, t8, t9, f4, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9
M^*	t1, t4, t5, f1, f3, f4	t2, t3, t6, t7, t8, t9, f2, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9
E^*	t1, t6, t7, t8, f1, f2, f4, f5	t2, t3, t4, t5, t9, f3, f6, f7, f8, f9

Do L^* , M^* and E^* meet the criteria of Day’s proof?

D2: yes, they separate the claims into two sets: those that satisfy and those that don’t.

D3: yes, at least some claims that satisfy each filter are true and some claims that don't are false. So they are truth tracking by D3 (but not by Axiom 4).

D4: Independence.

- Claim f2 satisfies L^* but does not satisfy M^*
- Claim f3 satisfies L^* but does not satisfy E^*
- Claim f1 satisfies M^* but does not satisfy E^*

D5: Mutual independence

- Claim f3 satisfies $L^* \cap M^*$ but does not satisfy E^*
- Claim f2 satisfies $L^* \cap E^*$ but does not satisfy M^*
- Claim f4 satisfies $M^* \cap E^*$ but does not satisfy L^*

Now consider the intersection of all three:

Filter	Satisfied	Not Satisfied
$L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$	t1, f1	t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8, t9, f2, f3, f4, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9

Day includes another premise specifically for the proof: P5 Non-vacuity of the conjunction. There exists at least one true claim that satisfies all three of L, M, and E. In this toy version of the triveritas this condition also holds by virtue of claim t1.

Day's claim is that " $L \cap M \cap E$ is epistemically superior to each of $L \cap M$, $L \cap E$, and $M \cap E$ " and as we have applied the same conditions to $L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$, then Day's reasoning holds for them also. By Day's definition of "epistemically superior", then yes $L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$ is "epistemically superior" because the only false positive it satisfies (f1) is satisfied by the other pairs! So that holds up, at least for this toy version.

However, the flaw in Day's definition of "epistemically superior" is now clear. As he only considers the problem of false positives, he has ignored false negatives i.e. true statements that have been excluded. "Epistemically superior" has ended up just meaning "smaller" and $L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$ ends up with a 50-50 split of true and false claims just like the other filters but with a smaller set.

Note that we are not attempting to disprove the idea that a combination of logical reasoning, mathematics and empirical observation is a productive approach to truth. What we are examining is whether Day's proof of his specific triveritas is effective. Critics of the argument above would be correct in saying that L^* , M^* and E^* do not resemble logic, maths or empiricism and that the selection of claims amount to stacking the deck. However, what we are demonstrating is that formal properties Day has proposed fail to capture relevant features of logical reasoning, mathematics and empirical observation.

Notably, it is possible to stack the deck in our toy triveritas to make things far worse for it. Again, the point of doing so is not as kind of global discreditation but to expose where aspects of logic, maths and empiricism have not been captured.

Consider this new toy version:

$C = \{t1, t2, t3, t4, t5, t6, t7, t8, t9, t10, t11, t12, t13, t14, t15, t16, t17, t18, t19, t20, t21, t22, t23, t24, t25, f1, f2, f3, f4, f5, f6, f7, f8, f9, f10, f11, f12, f13, f14, f15, f16, f17, f18, f19, f20, f21, f22, f23, f24, f25\}$

The table shows only the satisfied claims and the reader can assume any claim not listed was not satisfied.

Filter	Satisfied	Score
L^*	t1, t2, t3, t9, t10, t11, t12, t13, t14, f1, f2, f3, f4, f6	9 out of 14
M^*	t1, t4, t5, t15, t16, t17, t18, t19, f1, f2, f3, f4, f5	8 out of 13
E^*	t1, t6, t7, t8, t20, t21, t22, t23, t24, f1, f2, f3, f5, f6	9 out of 14

L^* , M^* and E^* now also are “truth tracking” by the higher standard of Axiom 4. There are equal numbers of false and true claims in C but each filter satisfies more true claims than false claims.

How does the intersection of all three look?

Filter	Satisfied	Score
$L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$	t1, f1, f2, f3,	1 out of 3

$L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$ still meets Day’s criteria for being epistemic superiority. There are no new false positives, at least one false positive was eliminated and at least one true claim was retained. Despite this $L^* \cap M^* \cap E^*$ is dog shit and is no longer “truth tracking” by the stricter standard of Axiom 4.

Day had anticipated that the D3 definition of truth tracking could lead to an issue like this and in the paper on the mathematical proof he added yet another “axiom”.

“a filter could exclude a large number of false claims and an even larger number of true claims, resulting in fewer false claims admitted but also a lower truth-density. The mathematical proof rules this out by invoking conditional truth-tracking (Axiom 5 of the Working Paper), which ensures that each filter preferentially removes false claims over true claims within the relevant set.”

Axiom 5 is included in the mathematical proof overtly to prevent the circumstance given above. However, it is not an axiom i.e. it is not a self-evident truth about the triveritas but rather a potential property of a set of filters that could only be determined empirically i.e. by examining over time whether the combination of filters reduced the truth density i.e. the ratio of true positives to false positives. This in itself is difficult as it would require some other standard of judging truth. Potentially, it could be done by looking historically at claims that initially met the criteria and the later, on further evidence or reworking of proofs, proved to be false.

Put another way, what Axiom 5 is effectively stating is that is that the combination of all three filters will be more effective than any one or any pair – which is what the proof is seeking to demonstrate. This is the begging the question fallacy and also one of the “horns” of Münchhausen Trilemma: circularity.

Would lower truth density occur with the actual triveritas? We strongly suspect that practically the triveritas is unworkable for other reasons (not least of which is the lack of clarity as to what Day means by “Logical Validity”) so the question is moot. However, the logical structure Day offers permits the possibility that the triveritas would lead somebody to accept a greater proportion of false positives than they would if they used only one of the criteria.

There is also an issue with Day’s model about the space of possible claims. For ease, our toy example used similar numbers of true and false claims. Does this reflect reality? If the universe

is finite then presumably the number of true claims about the universe is finite. However, there is no upper limit to the number of false claims other than the natural limits of time for people to actually make false claims. For example, Vox Day often discusses his IQ. It is safe to assume there is, to some degree of approximation, a true claim that Vox Day's IQ is x , for some value of x . There is no limit to values of x which would form a false claim. While there are upper and lower limits to IQ values, these are just reasons why a claim would be false (e.g. $x=-20$ or $x=100,000$). The potential number of false claims about Day's IQ vastly exceed the number of true claims.

Of course, practically, nobody would set about analysing claims about Day's IQ by systematically listing all the possible claims and testing each one. What is relevant here is whether Day's methodology makes sense and reflect an actual way of considering the truth of claims. To be fair to Day, he does acknowledge that the triveritas is "not a decision algorithm". That caveat doesn't resolve the problems we encountered with it though.

Why This Is Not Coherent(ism)

After discussing the proofs, Day moves onto challenging the idea that his method of epistemology is Coherentism. We agree that Coherentism is not a wholly accurate name for it as there are also elements of Foundationalism, Positivism and Coherentism mixed together in a way that manages to capture the flaws in each position and all to arrive at a conclusion that assigning truth to a claim is, at best, provisional.

Day argues as follows:

"The objection fails because it misidentifies the structure. In a coherentist web, every node is an internal belief, and justification consists in mutual support among internal beliefs. The system has no required contact with anything outside itself. A sufficiently large and internally harmonious web of beliefs counts as justified under coherentism even if every belief in the web is false, so long as they are mutually consistent."

As with much of this paper, we feel like we have to puzzle through what Day's thoughts are here. We suspect (but obviously don't know) that Day believes that there is a single set of Coherentist beliefs, whereas it is actually a wide range of approaches to truth that share a common feature. We are not familiar with a coherentist position that does not take empirical observation, logical reasoning and mathematics into account. We are aware of coherentist positions that are deeply connected to the mathematics of probability as applied to observed events.

A fuller survey of the variety within coherentist epistemology is available at the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy here <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/justep-coherence/>

Münchhausen's Revenge

From here on in, the paper largely repeats its earlier claims. We shan't cover all of the later sections as we have already discussed the key points but we will try to sum up the paper's failings.

The trilemma claims that justification always retreats into one of three outcomes:

1. *an infinite regress, which seems to arise from the necessity to go further and further back in the search for foundations, and which, since it is in practice impossible, affords no secure basis;*
2. *a logical circle in the deduction, which arises because, in the process of justification, statements are used which were characterized before as in need of foundation, so that they can provide no secure basis; and, finally,*

3. *the breaking-off of the process at a particular point, which, admittedly, can always be done in principle, but involves an arbitrary suspension of the principle of sufficient justification.*

How does the triveritas manage against the three “horns” of the trilemma?

Infinite Regress

The trilemma avoids infinite regress by resorting to vagueness. Day mentions axioms of logic but doesn't say which axioms he means. He mentions axioms of mathematics but again does not describe what he means. He alludes to the syllogistic method of Aristotle, which suggests older methods of logic but he also uses some set theory, which would be suggestive of approaches to logic at least up to the 1930s. He does accept that set theory is part of mathematics and the Zermelo–Fraenkel system of axioms are the most widely recognised axiomatisation of set theory and possibly the closest thing we have to a foundational set of axioms for mathematics. They are not without issues though, particularly the Axiom of Choice but reasonably Day's model is unlikely to need it. I would be interested to know if Day believes that mathematical infinities exist – it would be reasonable to believe they don't.

We can't say if Day has avoided infinite regress as we don't know what he means by logic or by the axioms of mathematics.

Logical circle of deduction

There may well be others but Axiom 5 is essentially a logical circle in which the core of the conclusion of a proof is introduced without justification as an axiom.

Breaking Off

The triveritas stops at “warranted assent”. It is reasonable to stop running down the rabbit hole of justification at some point and say that you think what you've already found is enough. What is odd, is that this is exactly what Day's triveritas does and then Day says that it isn't what it is doing. It's like advertising a car that can run without gasoline and when asked to explain how it works, saying that it runs off petrol.

Ahistorical nonsense

To add to the confusion, Day also argues that his combination of logic, maths and empirical observation is novel:

“The Scholastics had the logical tools. The mathematicians had the quantitative tools. The empiricists had the observational tools. Nobody put all three together and asked what happens when you require all three simultaneously. The answer is that the deepest problem in epistemology is solved. Not because the problem was trivial, not because it was misconceived, but because the third horn contains a fallacy that no one happened to notice for two thousand years. The fallacy is the amphiboly between termination and arbitrary termination. The Triveritas exposes the fallacy and provides the counterexample.”

Day is claiming that NOBODY combined logic, maths and empiricism until now. I feel confident in saying that the whole of western and indeed global science have been doing exactly that for hundreds of years. Does Day really think that Kepler wasn't using logic, as well as maths and observation of planets? Does Day think Newton was missing one of those three, if so, which one? This is a very bizarre claim because he also cites historical examples of “claims” (i.e. scientific theories) that do, in his opinion, satisfy the triveritas. Does he think each of these somehow accidentally included logic, or maths or observation?

Conclusion

Vox Day's paper on the Münchhausen Trilemma is both oddly repetitive and oddly triumphant. This may be due to Day's normal approach to argumentation but both these features are common aspect of writing produced by Large Language Models.

Day has said of his use of LLMs:

"I estimate that if you use AI correctly, you can augment your effective applied intelligence by about 1.5 SD. That's about 24 IQ points. I ran some of my recent projects, augmented and non-augmented, past 5 AI models, and they all produced results in much the same range."

He does appear to be producing more words but we are not convinced that they are evidence of especially high IQ.